

ANALYSIS OF A 14-16 AGE GROUP IRAQI AND TURKISH BOYS' SPORT-SPECIFIC ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION LEVEL

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to reveal 14-16 age group Iraqi and Turkish boys' achievement motivation differences in terms of various personal characteristics. Working group consists of 155 children (67 Iraqis, 88 Turks) in the 14-16 age group and being interested in football. Sport Specific Achievement Motivation Scale was used to obtain research findings. SPSS 22.0 program was used to analyze the data, the independent samples test was used for comparison of pair groups, One Way ANOVA test was used for comparison of multiple groups. As a result, while the Turkish children's power showing motive and motive to approach success was significantly high, it was found that the Iraqi children had higher scores in sub-dimensions of motive to avoid failure. Therefore, the motive to avoid failure of Iraqi children was higher than their achievement motivation scores and it can be said that Iraqi children tended to move away from competition conditions. This case may be due to personally negative reflection to children's psychology of internal disorder and negative events in their country and low self-confidence. In addition, according to obtained correlation results, it can be said that the physical structure of boys (height and body weight) increases power showing motive and motive to approach success but decreases motive to avoid failure.

Keywords: achievement motivation, soccer, child, Turk, Iraki

1. Introduction

The main aim of sportsmen and coaches in sports environment is to obtain a high performance in the competitions and ensure the continuity of that performance. Therefore, it is stated that achieving high performance includes not only a motoric process but also a good guidance and correct psychological preparation (Abakay, 2010). The goal and desire of the athletes is to ensure that their performances are at a certain level and to get a better performance than the previous ones every time. They display various behaviors in order to reach the goals they set in this process. These behaviors arise as physical, mental and psychological behaviours. The development of physical performance is possible through the use of innate abilities and proper working methods. However, psychological factors should not be ignored beside the physical efforts to increase sportive performance; it is thought that the most important of these psychological factors is the correct guidance, namely, motivation.

Motivation is seen as a force that enables people to continue their desired behavior in the direction of their emotions and needs in order to be able to do the desired behavior (Özülmüş, 2002).

Achievement motivation is defined as doing best when performing an action, overcoming obstacles, skillfully acting, and achieving nearly excellent success (Lawrence 1996). In other words, achievement motivation can be defined as resistance against failure, struggling until achieving success in a task (Cox 1990). While individuals tend to get closer to the situations that they take pleasure, feel happy and peaceful, they tend to move away from the opposite situations (Tiryaki and Gödelek, 1997). Achievement motivation is known to symbolize internal motivation, but it is also under the influence of a number of external factors. These factors are listed firstly as purpose suitability, material and moral awards, and reasons of action participation (Konter 1995).

Achievement motivation indicates overcoming the duties assigned to the individual, overcoming the difficulties encountered, achieving perfection, showing superior performance than the others and the effort put forth in order to be proud of his performance (Weinberg and Gould, 2015). The theory of achievement motivation explains for what purpose individuals participate in activities, the efforts they have made to overcome difficulties, and why they provide its continuity (Hayashi 1996).

It is mentioned that individuals with a high need for achievement do their job better and behave more carefully than the others. It is stated in the tests that individuals who have high achievement need, achieve high success than those who have low achievement need. In particular, the belief that the method followed in the child-rearing

style is important in this sense is prevailing. It is a common opinion of psychiatrists, achievement need of children who are obedient and whose freedom of decision making taken away is low and the experiences of younger life will affect their being a successful individual (Cüceloğlu, 1991).

In this study we have done, it is aimed to compare the sport-specific achievement motivation levels of 14-16 age group Iraqi and Turkish boys. For this purpose it has been sought answers to the following questions.

The levels of sport-specific achievement motivation

1. Is it differentiated according to nationality?
2. Is it differentiated according to age?
3. Is it differentiated according to sporting year?
4. Is it differentiated by grade level?
5. What is the correlation between the levels of achievement motivation, body weight and height measurements, and age, sporting year and grade levels?

2. Method

2.1 Research Method

This research is a descriptive study to determine the levels of sport-specific achievement motivation of Iraqi and Turkish children aged 14-16 years dealing with soccer. 155 children (88 Turkish, 67 Iraqi) aged between 14 and 16 active in various sports club infrastructures in Iraq and Turkey were selected as the research group. Some personal characteristics of the research group are given in table 1. It was applied on children. In the study, quantitative data were collected using the data collection tool (Sport-Specific Achievement Motivation Scale), which was introduced below. Data collected from the study group were analyzed and reported according to the demographics of the athletes and other variables discussed in the research. The Statistical Program for Social Sciences (SPSS 22.0) was used in statistical analysis.

Table 1: Distribution of personal characteristics of the study group

	N/%	Age	Height	Body Weight
Turkish	88 (%56.8)	15.23±.75	157.91±8.38	54.36±6.67
Iraqi	67 (%43.2)	15.25±.79	156.00±8.49	54.73±7.99
Total	155 (%100)	15.24±.77	156.96±8.44	54.55±7.33

2.2 Data Collection Techniques

The Sport-Specific Achievement Motivation Scale (SSAMS) was used to obtain the research data, this scale was developed by Willis (1982), and the validity and reliability

study of the scale was carried out by Tiryaki and Gödelek (1997) in Turkey. The scale was translated into Arabic to be applied to Iraqi children. The application was made in the club meeting rooms after training section on the basis of volunteerism, by explaining the importance and purpose of the study to the research group. The Sport-Specific Achievement Motivation Scale is a five-point Likert-type scale consisting of a total of 40 items. Scale items can be scored between 1 and 5 ("never, rarely, sometimes, usually, and always"). As a result of reliability analyzes performed by Tiryaki and Gödelek, alpha reliability coefficients for each sub-dimension of the scale were calculated separately. According to this, the reliability coefficients of the subscales were calculated as $r = 0.81$ for the subscale of Power Showing Motive (PSM), $r = 0.82$ for subscale of Motive to Approach Success (MAS), and $r = 0.80$ for the subscale of Motive to Avoid Failure (MAF).

2.3 Statistical Analysis of Data

The data obtained from the scale were first transferred to the computer environment and then calculated using the SPSS 22.0 package program. The arithmetic mean for analysing data, variance analysis for comparison of mean scores in unrelated measures (One-Way ANOVA, Independent samples t-test), (99), Spearman's rho (rs) correlation test was used to analyze the relationship between the two variables (Gamgam, 1998).

3. Results

In this part of the study, the results of variance analysis showing the differences in total scores, nationality, age, sporting year and grade variables obtained by the children of Turkish and Iraqi from the Sport-Specific Achievement Motivation Scale are given. In addition, findings related to the correlation between scores of children's achievement motivation sub factors and personal characteristics were included.

Table 2: Comparison of the scores of the research group obtained from the SSAMS

	Nation	N	Mean	Ss.	t	p
Power Showing Motive	Turkish	88	39.81	5.98	3.770	.000
	Iraqi	67	36.22	5.71		
Motive to Approach Success	Turkish	88	58.38	8.18	4.787	.000
	Iraqi	67	52.76	5.76		
Motive to Avoid Failure	Turkish	88	27.93	5.23	-2.513	.016
	Iraqi	67	30.30	6.49		

In Table 2 comparison of the scores obtained by the research group from the SSAMS sub-dimensions in terms of nationality is given. Significant differences were found in all sub-dimensions ($p < 0.05$). While there are meaningful differences in favor of Turkish children in the power showing motive and motive to approach success sub-dimensions, Iraqi children were found to have higher scores in the sub-dimension of motive to avoid failure.

Table 3: Comparison of the scores obtained from the scale by the research group in terms of age variable

Sub-dimensions	Nation		KT	Sd	Mean	F	p
Power Showing Motive	Turkish	Between-groups	73.776	2	36.888	1.034	.360
		In-group	3031.940	85	35.670		
		Total	3105.716	87			
	Iraqi	Between-groups	54.740	2	27.370	.835	.438
		In-group	2096.902	64	32.764		
		Total	2151.642	66			
Motive to Approach Success	Turkish	Between-groups	87.867	2	43.934	.652	.524
		In-group	5730.758	85	67.421		
		Total	5818.625	87			
	Iraqi	Between-groups	156.765	2	78.382	2.472	.092
		In-group	2029.414	64	31.710		
		Total	2186.179	66			
Motive to Avoid Failure	Turkish	Between-groups	20.525	2	10.262	.370	.692
		In-group	2359.066	85	27.754		
		Total	2379.591	87			
	Iraqi	Between-groups	49.788	2	24.894	.583	.561
		In-group	2732.242	64	42.691		
		Total	2782.030	66			

In Table 3, the comparison of the scores that the research group obtained from the scale sub-dimensions in terms of age variable is given. According to this, it was determined that the scores obtained from the scales did not differ in terms of ages of the research group ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4: Comparison of the scores obtained from the scale by the research group in terms of the sporting year variable

Sub-dimensions		KT	sd	KO	F	p	Significant Difference	
Power Showing Motive	Turkish	Between-groups	273.955	5	54.791			
		In-group	2831.761	82	34.534	1.587	.173	
		Total	3105.716	87				
	Iraqi	Between-groups	394.336	5	78.867			5 > 2, 3
		In-group	1757.306	61	28.808	2.738	.027	6 > 2, 3
		Total	2151.642	66				7 > 2, 3, 4
Motive to Approach Success	Turkish	Between-groups	970.741	5	194.148			5 > 2, 3
		In-group	4847.884	82	59.121	3.284	.009	6 > 2, 3
		Total	5818.625	87				7 > 2,3, 4
	Iraqi	Between-groups	76.711	5	15.342			
		In-group	2109.468	61	34.581	.444	.816	
		Total	2186.179	66				
Motive to Avoid Failure	Turkish	Between-groups	60.140	5	12.028			
		In-group	2319.450	82	28.286	.425	.830	
		Total	2379.591	87				
	Iraqi	Between-groups	150.403	5	30.081			2, 3 > 5, 6
		In-group	2631.626	61	43.141	.697	.023	2,3, 4 > 7
		Total	2782.030	66				

Groups; 1st group 2 years, 2nd group 3 years, 3rd group 4 years, 4th group 5years , 5thgroup 6 years, 6th group 7 years

In Table 4, the comparison of the scores that the research group obtained from the scale sub-dimensions in terms of sporting year is given.

In the sub-dimension of motive to approach success of Turkish children, there was a difference in the sporting year ($p < 0.05$). The Tukey LSD test was used to determine between which groups there was difference. In the sub-dimension of motive to approach success it has been determined that Turkish children who have been sporting for 5 and 6 years have achieved higher scores than those who have been sporting for 2 and 3 years, also the Turkish children who have been sporting for 7 years have achieved higher scores than those who have been sporting for 2,3 and 4 years. There was no difference in the sub-dimensions of motive to approach success and motive to avoid failure in terms of sporting year in Turkish children ($p > 0.05$).

Among Iraqi children, there were differences in terms of sporting year in the sub-dimensions of power showing motive and motive to avoid failure ($p < 0.05$). The Tukey LSD test was used to determine between which groups there was difference. In power showing motive sub-dimension, Iraqi children who have been sporting for 5 and 6 years have achieved higher scores than those who have been sporting for 2 and 3

years, also the children who have been sporting for 7 years achieved higher scores than those who have been sporting for 2, 3 and 4 years. In motive to avoid failure sub-dimension it has been determined that Iraqi children who have been sporting for 2 and 3 years achieved higher points than those who have been sporting for 5 and 6 years, also the Iraqi children who have been sporting for 2, 3 and 4 years have achieved higher scores than those who have been sporting for 7 years. Among Iraqi children, there was no difference in motive to approach success sub-dimension in terms of sporting year ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5: The scores obtained from the scale by the research group in terms of grade variable

Sub-dimensions		KT	sd	KO	F	p	Significant Difference
Power Showing Motive	Turkish	Between-groups	76.676	3	25.559	.709	.549
		In-group	3029.040	84	36.060		
		Total	3105.716	87			
	Iraqi	Between-groups	146.143	3	48.714	1.530	.215
		In-group	2005.498	63	31.833		
		Total	2151.642	66			
Motive to Approach Success	Turkish	Between-groups	99.076	3	33.025	.485	.021
		In-group	5719.549	84	68.090		
		Total	5818.625	87			
	Iraqi	Between-groups	51.470	3	17.157	.506	.679
		In-group	2134.709	63	33.884		
		Total	2186.179	66			
Motive to Avoid Failure	Turkish	Between-groups	58.259	3	19.420	.703	.553
		In-group	2321.332	84	27.635		
		Total	2379.591	87			
	Iraqi	Between-groups	244.376	3	81.459	2.022	.002
		In-group	2537.654	63	40.280		
		Total	2782.030	66			

Groups; 1st group 7th grade, 2nd group 8th grade, 3rd group 9th grade, 4th group 10th grade

In Table 5, the comparison of the scores that the research group obtained from the scale sub-dimensions in terms of grade variable is given. There was a difference in motive to approach success sub-dimension of Turkish children in terms of grade variable ($p < 0.05$). The Tukey LSD test was used to determine between which groups there was difference. It has been determined that Turkish children who are studying in 10th grade achieved higher scores than 7th and 8th grade students in motive to approach success sub-dimension. Among Turkish children, there was no difference in terms of grade

variable in sub-dimensions of power showing motive and motive to avoid failure ($p > 0.05$).

There was a difference in motive to avoid failure sub-dimension of Iraqi children in terms of grade variable ($p < 0.05$). The Tukey LSD test was used to determine between which groups there was difference. It was determined that the scores obtained by 10th grade students in the sub-dimension of motive to avoid failure were higher than those of 7th and 8th grades. Among Iraqi children, there was no difference in terms of grade variable in power showing motive and motive to approach success sub-dimensions ($p > 0.05$).

Table 6: Relationship between the personal characteristics of Turkish children and the scores obtained from the SSAMS

		PSM	MAP	MAF	Sporting Year	Grade Level	Age
Power Showing Motive	r	1	.356**	-.107	.190	.017	.153
	p		.001	.321	.077	.875	.155
Motive to Approach Success	r		1	-.212*	.355**	.099	.072
	p			.047	.001	.359	.506
Motive to Avoid Failure	r			1	-.074	.018	-.092
	p				.496	.864	.393

n=88, ** $p < 0.001$. * $p < 0.05$

In Table 6, the correlation between the personal characteristics of Turkish children and the scores obtained from the sub-dimensions of SSAMS is given. A moderate positive correlation was found between power showing motive and motive to approach success. In other words, it can be said that while power showing motive of Turkish children increases, motive to approach success increases, too. A weak negative correlation was found between the motive to approach success and motive to avoid failure. It can be said that while motive to approach success of Turkish children increases, motive to avoid failure decreases. A moderate positive correlation was found between the motive to approach success and sporting year. In other words, it can be said that as the sporting years of Turkish children increase, motive to approach success also increases. In Turkish children, there was no correlation between the scores obtained from the sub-dimensions of sport-specific achievement motivation scale and the grade level and age.

Table 7: Relationship between the personal characteristics of Iraqi children and the scores obtained from the SSAMS

		PSM	MAP	MAF	Sporting Year	Grade Level	Age
Power Showing Motive	r	1	.278*	-.273*	.395**	-.046	-.053
	p		.023	.025	.001	.714	.668
Motive to Approach Success	r		1	-.105	.108	.005	-.201
	p			.399	.383	.970	.103
Motive to Avoid Failure	r			1	-.164	-.008	.134
	p				.184	.947	.281

n=67, **p<0.001. *p<0.05

In Table 7, the correlation between the personal characteristics of Iraqi children and the scores obtained from the sub-dimensions of the SSAMS is given. There is a weak positive correlation between power showing motive and motive to approach success. In other words, it can be said that as power showing motive of Iraqi children increases, motive to approach success also increases. A weak negative correlation was found between the scores of power showing motive and motive to avoid failure. It can be said that while power showing motive of Iraqi children increases, the scores of motive to avoid failure decrease. A moderate positive correlation was found between the power showing motive and sporting years. In other words, it can be said that as sporting years of Iraqi children increase, power showing motive increases, too. In Iraqi children, there was no correlation between the scores obtained from the sub-dimensions of sport-specific achievement motivation scale and the grade level and age.

Table 8: Relationship between the height and body weights of the study group and the scores obtained from the SSAMS

		Turkish		Iraqi	
		Height	Body Weight	Height	Body Weight
Power Showing Motive	r	.456**	.518**	.223*	.332*
	p	.001	.000	.001	.016
Motive to Approach Success	r	.632**	.557**	.412**	.096
	p	.000	.000	.000	.440
Motive to Avoid Failure	r	-.132*	-.212*	-.599	-.749
	p	.023	.047	.065	.040

N_{Turkish} = 88, N_{Iraqi}=67, **p<0.001, *p<0.05,

In Table 8, the results of the correlation analysis between the height and body weights and the scores obtained by the research group from the achievement motivation scale is

given. While there is a moderate positive correlation between height and body weight of Turkish children and the power showing motive, a weak positive correlation is found for Iraqi children. While a moderate positive correlation was found between the motive to approach success and height in Iraqi children, both height and body weight was found to have a moderate positive relationship with the motive to approach success in Turkish children. While a weak negative correlation was found between motive to avoid failure and height and body weight in Turkish children, no correlation was found between motive to avoid failure and height and body weight in Iraqi children.

4. Discussion

In this study, which is aimed to compare the sport-specific achievement motivation levels of 14-16 age group Iraqi and Turkish children, significant differences were found in terms of nationality variables in all sub-dimensions of the scale.

Turkish children's power showing motives and motive to approach success scores were higher than those of Iraqi children. The motive to approach success and power showing motive are the motives that can rise by being proud of success in previous experiences and experiencing pleasure in life. Because the individual will want to experience the happiness that he has lived through stimuli that he has received from himself and from his surroundings after a success again in the same situation and this desire may increase his achievement motive. Therefore, it can be said that Turkish children more tend to participate in competitions. Çekin et al. stated that the motivations of Turkish children who engage in individual sports in the 14-16 age group are primarily to be healthy, to gain a place in society and to prove themselves (Çekin, Tatar, and Afyon 2001).

It is observed that Iraqi children reached a higher score than Turkish children in motive to avoid failure sub-dimension. Having a high motive to avoid failure is considered to be a negative situation. The motive to avoid failure is defined as a level of shame or humiliation which is experienced as a result of a failure. The motive to approach success and power showing motive are different from motive to avoid failure. For this reason, the motive to avoid failure may be low or high, while the motive to approach success and power showing motive are high. It is stated that particularly individuals who have an anxious personality tend to avoid competitive environments. In addition, social pressures arising from focusing too much on winning, fear of disability, and inability to meet expectations are the reasons that increase the level of anxiety. It can be said that one of the important sub-dimensions of motivation, the motive to avoid failure, is also closely related to anxiety (Konter, 1995).

It is seen that the relationship between success motivation and anxiety appears to be especially with the motive to avoid failure sub-dimension. In the nature of the motive to avoid failure, there is a perception that the result of the competition is dangerous which indicates that the person has an anxious personality. In other words, having anxious personality and having high-level of anxiety result in a tendency to avoid the competitive environments (Cox, 1990).

Therefore, according to the findings of the research, it can be said that Iraqi children tend to avoid competitive situations more than Turkish children. This may be due to the fact that internal disturbance and negative events in the country have affected the psychology of the children and that they have an anxious attitude towards life in the environment they live in.

Hayashi and Weiss (1994) stated that one of the reasons that affect the success motivation of the individuals is the cultural differences. Success motivation comes with the future expectations of the individual. The pleasure and satisfaction arising from succeeding the work being done increases the desire for future success in the sport and leads new expectations to be formed. Not every athlete can develop a high success motivation. The huge differences between expectations of sportsmen and the events that he/she experienced, the conflicts that are seen and felt are seen adversely affect the success motivation.

In terms of age variable, it was determined that there was no difference in scores obtained from sub-dimensions of achievement motivation scale of Iraqi and Turkish children. Soyer et al. (2010) did not find a significant correlation between the ages of the athletes and the achievement motivation.

A difference is determined in Turkish children's motive to approach success sub-dimension in terms of their sporting year. It is found that students who are doing 5 and 6 years of sports have achieved higher scores than those who have been doing sports for 2 and 3 years and students who are doing 7 years of sports have achieved higher scores than those who have been doing sports for 2, 3 and 4 years. This result can be attributed to the fact that children who are engaged in sports long term have more desire to experience the same pride and happiness which they have achieved by succeeding in sports.

Significant differences were found in the power showing motive and motive to avoid failures sub-dimensions in terms of sporting years in Iraqi children. It has been determined that Iraqi children who are doing sports for 5 or 6 years get higher scores than those who are doing sports for 2 and 3 years in power showing motive sub-dimension and those who are doing for 7 years get higher scores than 2, 3 and 4 years. It has been observed that Iraqi children who are doing sports for 2 or 3 years get higher

scores than those who are doing sports for 5 and 6 years in motive to avoid failure sub-dimension and those who are doing for 2, 3 and 4 years get higher scores than 7 years. According to the result, it seems that the two motives are inversely proportional to one another. It can be said that those who do sports for longer have a higher power showing motives, while those who are doing sports for less time have higher scores in motive to avoid failure and more likely afraid failure.

There was a difference in motive to approach success in terms of grade variable in the case of Turkish children. It is determined that 10th graders had higher scores than 7th and 8th graders in motive to approach success sub-dimension, whereas Iraqi children 10th graders had higher scores in motive to avoid failure sub-dimension than 7th and 8th graders.

There is a positive moderate correlation between the power showing motive of Turkish children and motive to approach success. In other words, it can be said that the motive to approach success of Turkish children increases when the power showing motive increases. A weak negative correlation was found between the motive to approach success and the motive to avoid failure. That is, it can be said that the motive to approach success of Turkish children increases while the motive to avoid failure decreases. A moderate positive correlation was found between motive to approach success and sporting year. In other words, it can be said that the motive to approach success increases as Turkish children's sporting years increase.

A weak positive correlation was found between the power showing motive and the motive to approach success in the case of Iraqi children. In other words, it can be said that the power showing motive of Iraqi children increases when the motive to approach success increases. A weak negative correlation was found between power showing motive and motive to avoid failure scores. In other words, it can be said that the scores of motive to avoid failure decreases while Iraqi children's power showing motive increases. There was a moderate positive correlation between power showing motive and sporting years. That is to say, as Iraqi children's sporting years increase, their power showing motives also increase.

While there was a moderate positive correlation between Turkish children's height and weight and power showing motives, a weak positive correlation is found in the case of Iraqi children. While a moderate positive correlation between motive to approach success and height was found in Iraqi children, there was a moderate positive correlation between motive to approach success of Turkish children and both their height and body weights. There was a weak negative correlation between motive to avoid failure and height and weights of Turkish children, whereas there was no correlation between motive to avoid failure and height and weights of Iraqi children.

As a result, significant differences were found in the sub-dimensions of sport-specific achievement motivation among 14-16 age group Iraqi and Turkish children. While Turkish children's power showing and motive to approach success scores were higher than those of Iraqi children, it was found that Iraqi children got higher scores in the motive to avoid failure sub-dimension. Therefore, it can be said that Iraqi children tend to avoid more from competitive environments than Turkish children. In addition, according to the correlation results obtained in the study, it can be said that well developed physical characteristics (height and body weight) in children increases power showing and motive to approach success while decreasing motive to avoid failure.

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